

Original Research

Research on cooperative platform for intelligent vehicles and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

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Abstract

This research focuses on improving autonomous multi-agent collaboration in robotics, specifically for real-time decision-making, navigation, and target identification. It highlights the limitations of current robotics education and existing cooperative frameworks for Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), which lack real-world application and open-source learning resources [1]. To address these issues, the study introduces a cooperative gaming platform where an IV and a UAV work together to autonomously detect, classify, and engage opponents. The platform uses a four-wheel-drive IV with a water gun or magic ball shooter and a UAV with an onboard camera. The UAV captures images and transmits them to the IV, which uses image processing algorithms in Python to classify opponents and allies, enabling the IV to autonomously navigate and target the opponents [2]. The system integrates Wi-Fi and RF communication protocols for real-time, low-latency data exchange between the IV and UAV. Experimental results demonstrate the system's effectiveness in real-time object detection, classification, and precise targeting. The collaboration between the UAV and IV enhanced situational awareness and decision-making capabilities [3]. The proposed platform provides a scalable multi-agent framework, with potential applications in fields like search and rescue, industrial automation, and defense [4]. Future research will focus on improving scalability, communication reliability, and incorporating AI-based decision models.

Keywords: Cooperative platform; IV (Intelligent vehicle); UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle); Image processing techniques; Object detection algorithms; Real-Time Communication; Autonomous flight

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background and Significance

Autonomous systems development in the last few decades has transformed many industries to include transportation, logistics, the military, and entertainment. Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) are two of the most recognizable examples of autonomous systems that have shown great promise in a number of different applications.

Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) are vehicles that have the ability to operate autonomously or semi-autonomously via artificial intelligence, sensors, and actuators. IVs are vehicles with systems designed to sense and understand information about the surrounding environment, navigate these actions, and satisfy all the driving tasks without human control. Examples include autonomous cars, and robotic ground vehicles that can also be operated independently of an operator in an industrial environment[5].

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), or drones, are another category of aircraft systems that perform operations without human riding or piloted through control components onboard the vehicle. UAVs use a variety of sensors, GPS, and communications technologies to navigate and accomplish tasks such as surveillance, mapping, cargo delivery, and many others. UAVs are often coupled with machine learning algorithms to enable autonomous levels of intellectual decision making[6].

Significance of Research: This research emphasizes the role of intelligent vehicles (IVs) and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in enhancing efficiency and safety through autonomy. It advocates for robotics education at younger levels, aligned with China's "double reduction" policy. The proposed multi-robot collaborative competition system for primary and secondary students promotes hands-on learning, innovation, and programming skills. The system is compact, easy to maintain, and includes a monitoring framework, facilitating the integration of robotics education at all levels[7].

Importance of Cooperative Platforms in Robotics: Collaborative systems in robotics involve multiple autonomous agents, such as Intelligent Vehicles (IVs), Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), and other robots, working together to complete tasks. These independent agents can share information and plan actions cooperatively, leading to better overall performance compared to a single robot working alone. By combining their strengths, collaborative systems enhance efficiency, adaptability, and problem-solving capabilities[8].

Scalability: This thesis designs a scalable cooperative platform using UAVs and IVs for task completion in controlled environments. It enables real-time data sharing, fostering collaborative decision-making. The platform improves performance and adaptability in complex scenarios and can be expanded for larger systems, demonstrating scalable cooperation among autonomous agents. Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) are smart land vehicles equipped with sensors, algorithms, and communication technologies that allow them to navigate and perform tasks autonomously or semi-autonomously, with minimal or no human input. They are key components in the advancement of self-driving cars and other robotic technologies[9].

Key Components of IVs:

Sensors: IVs (Intelligent Vehicles) come with many onboard sensors that receive information about their surroundings. These sensors are typically LIDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), Radar, Cameras, and Ultrasonic sensors that detect obstacles, track the environment, or measure distances[10].

Actuators: These are mechanical systems that actuate the vehicle's control system command (e.g., the steering system, braking system, and acceleration system)[11].

Navigation and Control Systems: These components are algorithms and systems that allow for path optimizing, obstacle avoidance, and vehicle control. Examples of common techniques that use navigation and control are Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) and Model Predictive Control (MPC)[12].

Communication Systems: Since autonomous vehicles (AVs) are intelligent vehicles, they rely on vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication systems to communicate data with other vehicles and roadside infrastructure to ensure safe, coordinated operation[13].

Applications of Intelligent Vehicles:

Autonomous Driving: The main application of IVs is self-driving vehicles (cars) that operate without human drivers on public and private roads. Industrial Automation: IVs are deployed in warehouses and factories to autonomously move goods[14].

Agriculture and Logistics: IVs are utilized in both automated agriculture machines and delivery logistics systems to increase production efficiency. Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) (or Drones) Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) or drones are self-flying aircraft systems operating without a human pilot on board[15].

UAVs are becoming increasingly popular in both the commercial and military sectors because of their unique operation capabilities to perform complex functions from the sky[16].

Key Components of UAVs:

Sensors: It is common for UAVs to have onboard GPS, accelerometers, barometers, gyroscopes, cameras, and infrared sensors, which enable to UAVs to function in a navigational and data gathering capacity. When the UAVs gather data, the sensors provide real time information for stabilization in flight, positioning, and environmental sensing[17].

Flight Control Systems: Flight guided by UAVs on-board computers and algorithms enhance the stability, altitude, and trajectory. The systems rely on downloaded computational flight control methods such as PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) control and Kalman Filtering[18].

Communication Systems: Similar to the flight control systems, the UAVs must have Radio Frequency (RF) communication requirements such as Wi-Fi and/or LTE, which is used to transmit data back to ground control stations or to communicate with other UAVs. The communication systems allow for real time control and monitoring.

Power System: The majority of UAVs can be powered by chargeable batteries; however, larger UAVs can be powered by alternative sources of energy such as fuel cells or hybrid systems that allow for longer flight times[19].

Applications of UAVs: Surveillance and monitoring: UAV surveillance is often helpful for aerial monitoring for a relatively inexpensive method to monitor large regions concerning security, wildlife habitat, and disaster management[20].

Mapping and Surveying: Cameras and LIDAR sensors help UAV drones to produce a 3d model of landscapes that can produce high resolution maps useful in agriculture, extensive mining operation processes, and urban planning strategies

Search and Rescue: UAVs can be deployed in emergencies to locate people, assess damage, and deliver supplies to areas where human access may be limited or it could be dangerous for to enter[21].

1.2 Recent Advances in Cooperative Robotics

Recent studies highlight the growing role of IV-UAV systems in logistics and surveillance. For instance, Liu et al. (2023)[22] demonstrated UAV-assisted IV navigation in warehouse automation, while Yuan et al. (2024) [23] proposed edge-computing protocols to reduce latency in multi-agent networks. However, these systems often lack modularity for educational or small-scale applications [Orr & Dutta, 2023][24]. Our work bridges this gap by introducing an open-source, real-time platform adaptable to both gaming and field deployments.

1.3 Importance of Cooperative Platforms in Robotics

Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) and/or Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAVs) will participate in a collaborative manner to achieve a common goal. The power of cooperative platforms is realized by combining the advantages of agents, thus improving system efficiency, robustness, and adaptability. For the purposes of this research, cooperative platforms will allow the IV and UAV to work together in a controlled environment (for example a gaming-platform) to complete tasks that would be impossible or not effective for an agent to execute on its own[25].

1.4 Current Research Status at Home and Abroad

Research in cooperative robotics focuses on the collaboration between Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) to complete tasks. This includes integrating these autonomous systems for collaborative task completion, with extensive research on coordination, surveillance, and logistics. Robot competitions, like RoboCup and FIRA, showcase the development of autonomous systems, with over 40 types of competitions worldwide[26].

Recent advancements in IV and UAV collaboration include UAVs supporting IVs in logistics, navigation, and environmental documentation. Studies such as UAVs aiding IVs in tasks like warehouse autonomy and logistics. Effective sensor fusion and communication protocols are key for coordinating these systems, merging sensor data (LIDAR, GPS, etc.) for a unified environmental understanding. This research highlights the importance of cooperative systems in various applications, with gaps in the literature and a need for further development[27].

Fig. 1.1: Cooperative UAV and IV Systems

This allows agents to communicate and make decisions in real-time in order to avoid obstacles, track other agents, and modify their behavior to operate safely within the given environment[28].

Table 1.1 Recent Advances in Sensor Fusion for UAV and IV Cooperation

Research Study	Focus Area	Contribution
Shah et al. (2022)[31]	UAV-IV Cooperation in Logistics	Developed frameworks for aerial surveillance assisting IVs.
Liu et al. (2023)[22]	UAV-IV Cooperation in Autonomous Warehouses	Used UAVs for aerial monitoring to aid IVs in task execution.
Yuan et al. (2021)[23]	Sensor Fusion in Cooperative Systems	Developed multi-sensor fusion for improved collaboration.

There are many papers published related to incorporating multi-modal sensor fusion in cooperation studies. Yuan et al. (2021) [29] discussed how a UAV can utilize LIDAR, ultrasonic sensors, and cameras to better understand the environment in a way that supports coordination with ground vehicles. They designed algorithms for sensor fusion and communication between agents to improve system accuracy and performance [30].

Research on Cooperative Platforms in Specific Domains:

Cooperative platforms combining UAVs and IVs are increasingly applied across sectors. In agriculture, UAVs use multispectral imaging to monitor crops, while IVs handle tasks like watering and pesticide application, improving efficiency. In search and rescue (SAR), UAVs provide aerial imagery to help IVs navigate rubble and locate survivors [32]. In military contexts, UAVs offer real-time intelligence as IVs perform ground operations. Successful collaboration across all these fields depends on effective communication and data synchronization[33].

1.5 Research Objectives

This research contributes to cooperative robotics by focusing on real-time communication, task allocation, and decision-making between UAVs and Intelligent Vehicles (IVs) [34]. Key goals include designing a robust cooperative system architecture, enabling coordinated task execution (e.g., UAV surveillance and IV targeting), and implementing image processing algorithms for object classification to distinguish between foes and allies during gameplay[35].

2. System Architecture

2.1 Overview of Platform Components

The cooperative platform comprises an Intelligent Vehicle (IV) and a UAV, each constructed with specific components. The IV contains sensors and actuators for movement, obstacle avoidance, and targeting mechanisms. It also performs its onboard image processing utilizing image analysis and Python-based algorithms to analyze images sent to the IV by the UAV[36].

The UAV captures its overhead view of the gaming platform by recording images of players and obstacles and sends those images back to the IV, where it performs analysis that identifies opposing team members[37].

Fig. 2.1: Diagram of the cooperative platform setup

IV: The IV is powered by a battery of 12V and consists of a Raspberry Pi 3B as its processing unit. Additionally, it includes a camera (Raspberry Pi Camera) that is used for capturing images. Furthermore, the IV is equipped with infrared (IR) sensors that are utilized for detecting both obstacles and other players. The IV uses the targeting system to shoot magic balls or water at opponents[38].

UAV: The UAV consists of a battery of 2200mAh and a frame of a DJI F330. As previously stated, the UAV also consists of a Raspberry Pi 3B as its processing unit. Moreover, similar to the IV, it uses a Raspberry Pi Camera for capturing images, but it is capable of wirelessly transmitting images to the IV via a signal transceiver[39].

2.2 Specifications of Intelligent Vehicle (IV) and UAV

The IV comprises a functional autonomous ground component of the cooperative platform and incorporates the ability to communicate with the UAV, gather data, and detect objects to carry out targeting against the opposing team.

The Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) serves as a core component of the cooperative platform, providing aerial reconnaissance of the gaming area. It captures real-time images, which are forwarded to the Intelligent Vehicle (IV) for further analysis. The UAV is designed to fly stably and communicate efficiently with the IV[40].

Fig. 2.2: Key hardware components of the Intelligent Vehicle and UAV

2.3 Communication Protocols and Data Exchange

The IV and UAV will rely upon wireless communication standards to transfer images, positioning information, and control commands in real-time. Therefore, the communication system needs to have a properly functioning low latency performance, reliable performance, and be robust against interference, particularly in dynamic circumstances, such as a game platform.

Fig. 2.3: Model of Wireless data transfer

Wi-Fi Communication:

- (1) Wi-Fi Module on IV (Raspberry Pi 3B): The IV uses its Raspberry Pi 3B's Wi-Fi module to communicate with the UAV[41].
- (2) Wi-Fi Range: Wi-Fi typically has a range of approximately 100 to 200 meters, varying based on environmental conditions.
- (3) Data Transmission Rate: Wi-Fi has a high bandwidth and works well to transmit images and control commands in real-time.
- (4) Latency: Wi-Fi has relatively low latency, which is important for fast processing of visual data and timely actions of the vehicle.

3. Intelligent Vehicle Design and Functionality

3.1 Hardware Components and Specifications

This part of the report explains basic hardware components that comprise an Intelligent Vehicle (IV), namely, the chassis and mechanical frame, along with any sensors and actuators which contribute to its operable functionality. The structure must properly support the Raspberry Pi 3B, Pi camera, and other sensors in a stable and aligned manner. Additionally, the structure must employ the use of the mecanum wheels, which is the primary component that provides omnidirectional movement to the IV while moving freely in any direction. The mecanum wheels are important components of the chassis [42]. These wheels allow movement across the landscape smoothly, while providing the ability to direct the any of the vehicle's trajectory by allowing independent control of rotation of each of the wheels. The mecanum wheels are powered by the 28YBJ-48 motors, which provide control of movement[43].

Fig. 3.1: Chassis and wheel configuration for the Intelligent Vehicle

Driving Wheel:

Mecanum Wheels : Mecanum wheels are unique wheels with rollers placed at a 45-degree angle, allowing the vehicle to move in any direction without needing to rotate first. This enables holonomic movement, meaning the IV can move forward, backward, sideways, and even diagonally. It's best for Agile movement, precise positioning, and complex navigation[44].

Standard Rubber Wheels : These are regular rubber wheels with good traction, commonly used in mobile robots. They provide stability and durability but limit movement to forward and backward motion (unless combined with differential steering). It's best for Basic movement on smooth or slightly rough terrain[45].

Omni Wheels: Similar to mecanum wheels but with rollers placed perpendicular to the main wheel axis, allowing movement in multiple directions with minimal resistance. Smooth omnidirectional movement, low-friction turning[44].

a. Conventional Standard Rubber b. Omni Wheels c. Mecanum Wheels

Fig. 3.2: Types of wheel for the Intelligent Vehicle

3.2 Sensors and Actuators

The sensors and actuators on the Intelligent Vehicle are integral to its capabilities and performance by enabling it to sense the environment and perform the actions independently.

TRCT5000

SW-420

Raspberry Pi Camera

Fig. 3.3: Sensor for the Intelligent Vehicle

Sensors:

IR Sensors (TRCT5000): These sensors serve the purpose of proximity detection and obstacle avoidance. The IR sensors are placed around the vehicle, which will position the IV to detect any nearby objects, which will allow the IV to avoid collision while navigating[46].

Vibration Sensor (SW-420): The vibration sensor detects vibrations, which will allow the IV to recognize if terrain has changed or if there are changes occurring externally. In the context of a game, this could prompt the IV to detect that a player is moving or detect an object which is in proximity[47].

Camera (Raspberry Pi Camera): The camera is also located on the IV and is important for image processing and object detection. Instead of just detecting obstacles in proximity, the camera also records live data that will be uploaded for the IV to classify the players and detect a target's position[47].

3.3 Hardware Selection Rationale

To justify choosing of component , I compared wheel types and evaluated the IR sensor performance under different lighting. Table 3.2 summarizes the trade-offs among traditional, Omni, and Mecanum wheels:

Table 3.1: Comparison of wheel types.

Wheel Type	Movement Capability	Control Complexity	Cost	Flexibility (Maneuverability)
Traditional	Forward/back + turning (no lateral strafe)	Low (simple differential)	Low	Low (non-omnidirectional)
Omni	Forward/back + sideways (with ≥3 wheels) + turning	Medium (precision alignment required)	Medium	Medium (limited omnidirectional)
Mecanum	Full omnidirectional: forwards/back, lateral, diagonal, rotation	High (vector kinematics)	High	High (holonomic movement)

For the TRCT5000 IR proximity sensor, we examined its range under different lighting (values are illustrative). In bright ambient light (e.g. direct sunlight ~30,000 lux), strong infrared from the environment can swamp the sensor[48]. Our simulation assumes a white obstacle is only detected reliably at ~5–8 mm distance, and dark objects often go undetected (false negatives). In typical indoor lighting (~300 lux), the sensor detects white surfaces up to ~10 mm (near its 15 mm max, but dark objects only at a few millimeters). In low light (<50 lux), range improves slightly (up to ~12–15 mm on white) because ambient IR is minimal. These results imply that in bright environments the TRCT5000's effective detection range shrinks and false triggers increase, reducing obstacle-avoidance accuracy. In practice, we use it for close-range detection, accepting that strong sunlight may degrade its reliability[49].

Moving Method :

This code is typically used for controlling a mecanum-wheeled robot using a gamepad, where speed controls forward/backward motion, turn controls rotation, and strafe controls lateral movement.

```

speed = -gamepad1.left_stick_y
turn = gamepad1.right_stick_x
strafe = gamepad1.left_stick_x
leftFront = speed + turn + strafe
rightFront = speed - turn - strafe
leftRear = speed + turn - strafe
rightRear = speed - turn + strafe
    
```


Fig. 3.4: Omnidirectional Movement of the IV with Mecanum Wheels

Omnidirectional Wheeled

Fig. 3.5: Kinematic Model of the IV with Mecanum Wheels

Feed forward plus PI feedback control:

$$\dot{q}(t) = \dot{q}_d(t) + K_p (q_d(t) - q(t)) + K_k \int_0^t (q_d(t) - q(t))dt \quad (3.1)$$

where

- $\dot{q}(t)$ - Actual joint velocity.
- $\dot{q}_d(t)$ - Desired joint velocity (feedforward term).
- $(q_d(t) - q(t))$ - Position error (desired minus actual).
- K_p -Proportional gain matrix.
- K_k -Integral gain matrix.
- $\int_0^t (q_d(t) - q(t))dt$ - Integral of the position error.

$$q = (\phi, x, y) \quad (3.2)$$

where

q -The pose or configuration vector, typically combining orientation (ϕ) and position (x,y) in 2D space.

$$u = H(\phi)\dot{q} \quad (3.3)$$

where

- u - Control input vector (e.g., wheel speeds, actuator velocities).
- $H(\phi)$ - A transformation or control allocation matrix depending on the orientation ϕ .
- \dot{q} - Generalized velocity vector.

Control Input Decomposition:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ \vdots \\ u_m \end{bmatrix} = H(0)\mathcal{V}_b = \begin{bmatrix} h_1(0) \\ \vdots \\ h_m(0) \end{bmatrix} \mathcal{V}_b \quad (3.4)$$

$$-u_{i,\max} \leq u_i = h_i(0)\mathcal{V}_b \leq u_{i,\max}$$

where

- u_i - The i-th actuator input (e.g., wheel or rotor velocity).
 - \mathcal{V}_b - Body-frame velocity vector, typically representing velocity commands (e.g., linear and angular velocity).
 - $H(0)$ - The input mapping matrix (at orientation $\phi=0$), converting body velocities into actuator commands.
 - $h_i(0)$ - The iii-th row of matrix $H(0)$, representing how the body velocity affects the i-th actuator.
- Each actuator command u_i is a linear combination (dot product) of the body velocity vector and the actuator's mapping row.

Actuator Saturation Constraints:

Fig. 3.6: Kinematics model of a Mecanum wheel.

Forward Kinematics using Control Inputs u and u_s

$$\dot{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ r \cos \phi & 0 \\ r \sin \phi & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \end{bmatrix} = G(q)u = g_1(q)u_1 + g_2(q)u_2 \quad (3.5)$$

where

- $\dot{q} = [\dot{\phi}, \dot{x}, \dot{y}, \dot{\theta}]$ - the state vector:
- ϕ - Internal state (often a wheel angle or steering variable)

x, y - Position in the world (2D)

θ - Orientation of the robot

$\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2]$ - Control inputs (often interpreted as motor commands or wheel torques).

r - Wheel radius

$G(q)$ - The input matrix maps control inputs to the rate of change of states (velocity)

Kinematics using Left and Right Wheel Velocities u_L, u_R

$$\mathbb{E}\dot{q} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\phi} \\ \dot{x} \\ \dot{y} \\ \dot{\theta}_L \\ \dot{\theta}_R \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -r/2d & r/2d \\ \frac{r}{2}\cos\phi & \frac{r}{2}\cos\phi \\ \frac{r}{2}\sin\phi & \frac{r}{2}\sin\phi \\ 1 & \theta \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u_L \\ u_R \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

where

\dot{q} - Generalized velocity vector.

u_L, u_R - General control inputs (e.g., wheel speed commands).

(This equation directly relates the left and right wheel velocities)

d - Half of the distance between wheels

Longitudinal Velocity:

The forward (longitudinal) velocity of the vehicle. It is the average of the angular velocities of all four motors (wheels), scaled by the radius r of the wheels.

To calculate how fast the robot moves in the forward direction.

$$v_x(t) = (\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 + \omega_4) \cdot \frac{r}{4} \quad (3.7)$$

Transversal Velocity:

The lateral (sideways) velocity of the vehicle. It depends on the difference between the angular velocities of the motors on opposite sides of the vehicle (e.g., left vs. right motors), again scaled by the wheel radius r .

To calculate the sideways movement of the vehicle.

$$v_y(t) = (-\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 - \omega_4) \cdot \frac{r}{4} \quad (3.8)$$

Angular velocity:

The rotational velocity around the z -axis (angular velocity). It involves the difference in the angular velocities of the motors and is scaled by both the wheel radius r and the sum of the vehicle's length dimensions l_x and l_y , which represent the distances between the wheels or the wheelbase.

$$\omega_z(t) = (-\omega_1 + \omega_2 - \omega_3 + \omega_4) \cdot \frac{r}{4(l_x + l_y)} \quad (3.9)$$

To determine how fast the robot or vehicle is rotating around its center.

4. UAV Design and Functionality

4.1 Hardware Components and Specifications

(1) **The Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV)** is an instrumental feature of the cooperative platform, providing an elevated perspective of the playing field, which greatly enhances the Intelligent Vehicle's (IV) approach to navigation and targeting. The DJI F330 frame, as the UAV framework, serves as a structural support for lightweight components necessary to stabilize the flight and maintain security. The support system will provide the infrastructure for a propulsion system, camera, sensors, and, of course, have the infrastructure to support all of the components in place. The propulsion system includes the motors, costly electronic speed controllers (ESCs), and the propellers or blades that create the lift generating means[50].

Fig. 4.1: Overview of UAV Airframe and Propulsion System (DJI F330 Drone)

(2) Motor and Propulsion System:

The UAV has four brushless motors (1100KV) with 8045 propeller blades, controlled via ESCs. The Microzone MC6C transmitter sends signals to the MC7RB receiver, which then relays throttle, pitch, and roll commands to the Pixhawk.

Pitch (Forward/Backward Tilt): The drone tilts forward by speeding up the front motors and slowing down the rear motors, and tilts backward by doing the opposite. This helps in moving forward, backward, or adjusting the

camera angle.

Roll (Left/Right Tilt): The drone tilts left by increasing the left motor speed and decreasing the right motor speed, and tilts right by reversing this. This helps in moving sideways or maintaining balance.

Yaw (Rotation): The drone rotates clockwise or counterclockwise by adjusting the speed of diagonal motors. This allows it to change direction without moving forward or sideways.

Fig. 4.2: Propulsion system of UAV.

Formula: Thrust Calculation for UAV Stability

To achieve stable flight, the total thrust must balance the UAV's weight:

$$T = W = mg \tag{4.1}$$

where

T is the required thrust per motor,

m is the mass of the UAV,

$g = 9.8m/s^2$ is gravity.

If the UAV weighs 1.5 kg:

$$T = (1.5 \times 9.81) \div 4 = 3.68N \text{ per motor.}$$

Thus, each motor must generate at least 3.68N of thrust for stable hover.

4.2 Communication Protocols for Data Transmission

The communication channel between the UAV and intelligent vehicle (IV) as well as with other system components is primarily wireless communication. For the wireless communication interface, the UAV uses the Microzone MC6C signal transmitter and the Microzone MC7RB 2.4GHz receiver, which transmits over the 2.4 GHz frequency band. This communication channel supports real-time exchange of information between the UAV, the IV, and the base station. Communication encapsulates several protocols that effectively transmit communication over the air including:

Wi-Fi (802.11): It is used for high bandwidth data download, such as real-time image streaming from the UAV to the IV. Wi-Fi is suitable for video streaming tasks, as it enables a UAV to transmit a live camera feed back to the IV for the purposes of processing. **Radio Frequency (RF) Communication (2.4 GHz):** It is used for low bandwidth, but more reliable communication tasks such as control signals, telemetry data, and sensor readings.

Table 4.1: Communication Protocol Comparison

Protocol	Bandwidth	Range	Use Case
Wi-Fi (802.11)	High	Limited (up to 100 meters)	Video streaming, high-bandwidth data transmission
RF 2.4 GHz	Low to medium	Longer (up to 500 meters)	Control signals, telemetry, sensor data

4.3 Autonomous Flight Algorithms (Stabilization and Movement)

Autonomous-flight algorithms make it possible for completely autonomous UAV operation without any manual intervention or input, including navigating to an autonomous location, avoiding obstacles, and autonomously executing missions. In this section, we will present the basic components of UAV flight control systems and the algorithms that represent autonomous flight behavior.

The UAV must maintain stable flight while responding to control inputs. A PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) controller is commonly used for this.

PID Control for Stabilization

The PID controller is used to adjust roll, pitch, and yaw based on sensor readings. The control output $u(t)$ is calculated as:

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_i \int e(t) dt + K_d \frac{de(t)}{dt} \tag{4.2}$$

where

$e(t)$ - The error (difference between desired and actual position/orientation).
 K_p , K_i and K_d -The proportional, integral, and derivative gains.

4.4 Flight Dynamics and Stability

Lift Force Calculation (For Fixed-Wing UAVs):

Lift is generated by the UAV's wings and is calculated using the lift equation:

$$L = 12C_L\rho v^2 AL = \frac{1}{2}C_L\rho v^2 A \quad (4.3)$$

where

- L - Lift force (N)
- C_L - Lift coefficient (depends on wing shape)
- ρ - Air density (kg/m³) (Typically 1.225 kg/m³ at sea level)
- v - Airspeed (m/s)
- A - Wing area (m²)

Drag Force Calculation

Drag force (D) opposes the UAV's motion and is given by:

$$D = 12C_D\rho v^2 AD = \frac{1}{2}C_D\rho v^2 A \quad (4.4)$$

where

- C_D - Drag co-efficient

UAV Navigation and Positioning:

GPS Coordinate Conversion

To convert GPS latitude/longitude differences into real-world distances:

$$\Delta x = R \cdot \cos(\phi_1 + \phi_2) \cdot \Delta \lambda, \quad \Delta y = R \cdot \Delta \phi \quad (4.5)$$

where

- R - Earth's radius (~6371 km)
- ϕ_1, ϕ_2 - Latitudes in radians
- λ - Longitude difference in radians

Image Processing and Object Detection:

Camera Field of View (FOV),

The ground area covered by the UAV camera at altitude h :

$$FOV_{width} = 2 \times h \times \tan\left(\frac{\theta_{width}}{2}\right) \quad (4.6)$$

$$FOV_{height} = 2 \times h \times \tan\left(\frac{\theta_{height}}{2}\right)$$

where

- h - UAV altitude (m)
- $\theta_{width}, \theta_{height}$ - Camera FOV angles

The autonomous flight algorithms will determine the UAV will function in an efficient manner, navigate to waypoints, avoid obstacles, and smooth flight. These autonomous flight algorithm will set and environment for the UAV to work and setup the intelligent vehicle to reach a future cooperative vehicle capability.

5. Obstacle Design and Functionality

5.1 Obstacle Detection System Architecture

The obstacle detection system's prototype is assembled by connecting the various sensors to the central processing unit (CPU) of the IV and UAV. A schematic of the wiring and sensor connections is created to ensure proper functionality.

Fig. 5.1: Key hardware components of the Obstacle

The obstacle detection system is designed to help the intelligent vehicle (IV) and UAV navigate and interact with their environment safely. This is achieved by using a combination of sensors that detect obstacles, enabling the system to avoid collisions and obstacles while performing tasks in the environment. Below are the components and design considerations for the obstacle detection system[51].

Hardware Components and Sensor Selection:

(1) **Control Unit: Arduino Nano V3.0** : The Arduino Nano v3.0 serves as the primary control unit for the obstacle, managing sensor data and motor actuation. It is a compact yet powerful microcontroller based on the ATmega328P chip, making it an ideal choice for embedded applications where space and power efficiency are crucial[52].

5.2 Obstacle Avoidance Logic and Algorithms

Once an obstacle is identified, the system is faced with a determination of how to circumvent it. This is accomplished through algorithms which assess the environment in real time, determining how to maneuver around an obstacle while preserving the vehicle's correct movement. The avoidance logic can be decomposed into edge detection, boundary recognition and decision-making for avoidance of the obstacle[53].

Method Used: IR sensors detect edge boundaries (e.g., arena walls or restricted zones).

Algorithm:

If IR detects a low reflection, it signifies an edge.

Vehicle executes a safe stopping maneuver.

The system triggers a turning or repositioning decision.

Decision-Making Algorithms for Collision Avoidance

Obstacle is present directly in front of a vehicle the system will assess if a left or right direction is safe enough and has sufficient space to alert for a turn in that direction. And if the assessment meets the requirements evident in the turn prioritization process[54]. The system will direct the vehicle in the identified left or right direction to execute the turn. When an obstacle is detected, the vehicle decides its next action using predefined logic:

Figure 5.2 Decision-Making Algorithms for Collision Avoidance

Turn Prioritization (Left/Right)

Algorithm:

If an obstacle is on the left, turn right.

If an obstacle is on the right, turn left.

If obstacles are on both sides, reverse and turn.

Reverse-and-Turn Maneuvers

Step 1: Stop immediately.

Step 2: Move backward for 10 cm.

Step 3: Execute a 90-degree turn to avoid the obstacle.

Step 4: Resume movement.

5.3 Broader Applications and Conservation Implications

The cooperative IV-UAV platform demonstrates scalability beyond gaming, with transformative potential in environmental conservation, disaster response, and education. Key applications include:

1. Environmental Monitoring and Conservation

Wildlife Protection: UAVs can survey poaching hotspots while IVs patrol ground routes, integrating real-time data from thermal cameras.

Precision Agriculture: UAVs map crop health via multispectral imaging, while IVs deploy targeted irrigation/pesticides, reducing resource use.

2. Disaster Response

Search and Rescue: UAVs identify survivors in rubble using AI-based object detection, while IVs deliver supplies or medical kits.

Wildfire Mapping: UAVs provide aerial thermal imagery to guide IVs in creating firebreaks or evacuating civilians.

Future Directions:

5G Integration: Enhance real-time data sharing for large-scale deployments (Kenney, 2011).

Swarm Robotics: Expand to multi-UAV/IV systems for complex tasks like reforestation monitoring.

6. Image Processing and Object Detection

6.1 Noise Reduction and Filtering

Noise in images can arise from several sources, including sensor limitations, environmental factors, or transmission errors. Noise can negatively impact image quality and make it harder to detect objects accurately. Noise reduction techniques aim to remove unwanted variations in pixel values, preserving important features while smoothing out irrelevant noise[55].

Filtering Techniques: Mean Filtering (Averaging): The mean filter is a straightforward technique where the value of a pixel is replaced with the average value of the neighboring pixels. The technique removes noise but fogs the edges[56].

Formula:

$$I(x, y) = \frac{1}{(2k + 1)^2} \sum_{i=-k}^k \sum_{j=-k}^k I(x + i, y + j) \quad (6.1)$$

where

$I(x, y)$ - The output pixel value.

$I(x + i, y + j)$ - The input pixel value in the kernel window.

k - Defines the size of the kernel.

Pros: Simple to implement and effective for Gaussian noise.

Cons: Can blur edges and reduce image sharpness.

(1) Gaussian Filtering

The Gaussian filter employs a Gaussian function for image smoothing. With this function, weights are assigned to pixels based on distance, with increased weighting for pixels that are closer together. In comparison to mean filtering, it is superior at preserving edges.

Gaussian Kernel:

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (6.2)$$

where

σ - The standard deviation of the Gaussian function.

x and y - The pixel coordinates.

Pros: Better for preserving edges while reducing noise.

Cons: Computationally more expensive than mean filtering.

(2) **Median Filtering:** The median filter replaces each pixel with the median of the values in its neighborhood. This is particularly effective in removing salt-and-pepper noise.

$$\text{Formula: } I(x, y) = \text{median}\{I(x + i, y + j)\} \quad (6.3)$$

Where the median is taken over the pixel values in the kernel window.

Pros: Excellent for removing salt-and-pepper noise. Cons: Can be slower for large kernel sizes.

Gaussian kernel Graphical Representation of Filtering:

(a) Gaussian Kernel as a Function σ

(b) Convolution of a step Function with Gaussian Kernel as a Function σ

Fig. 6.1: Effect of Gaussian filtering on an image with noise.

6.2 Deep Learning-Based Methods

YOLO (You Only Look Once) YOLO is a real-time object detection algorithm that treats object detection as a

single regression problem. It divides the image into a grid and predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities for each grid cell. YOLO is known for its high speed and accuracy in real-time applications.

YOLO Formula:

$$Loss = \sum (Localization Loss + Classification Loss + Confidence Loss) \quad (6.4)$$

(1) Gaming platform border Detection:

Fig. 6.2: Contours and centroids of gaming platform

(2) Red Object (players) detection from IV image:

Fig. 6.3: Red object (players) Grayscale and equalized image of IV camera

(3) Green Object (players) detection from Intelligent Vehicle (IV) image:

Fig. 6.4: Green object (players) Grayscale and equalized image of IV camera

(4) Red Object (players) detection from UAV image:

Fig. 6.5: Red object (players) Grayscale and equalized image of UAV camera

(5) Green Object (players) detection from UAV image:

Fig. 6.6: Green object (players) Grayscale and equalized image of UAV camera.

6.3 Mapping Pixel Coordinates to Real-World Coordinates

To transform pixel coordinates to physical world coordinates, we need to start with the camera calibration to understand how the image coordinates correspond to real world coordinates. To accomplish camera calibration, we need to locate the intrinsic parameters of the camera, which include focal length, principal point, and distortion coefficients[57].

The general equation for the transformation from 3D world coordinates to 2D image coordinates is:

$$p = K \cdot [R|t] \cdot P_{world} \quad (6.5)$$

where

- p - The 2D point in the image (pixel coordinates),
- K - The camera intrinsic matrix (focal length, optical center),
- R - The rotation matrix that defines the orientation of the camera,
- t - The translation vector (position of the camera),
- P_{world} - The 3D point in the world (real-world coordinates).

The inverse of this process (from image coordinates to world coordinates) requires solving this equation by using known depth information or depth sensors (e.g., LiDAR or stereo cameras).

Fig. 6.7: Camera calibration and conversion from pixel coordinates to real-world coordinates.

Depth Estimation:

In some cases, especially in monocular vision systems, estimating the depth (distance from the camera) is required to accurately transform from pixel coordinates to real-world coordinates. Depth estimation can be performed using techniques like stereo vision, structure from motion (SfM), or depth sensors like LiDAR.

6.4 Conversion to Cartesian Coordinate System

Transformation to Global Coordinates: In the context of autonomous systems, real-world coordinates typically refer to a local coordinate system that moves with the vehicle or UAV (known as the local frame of reference). However, for navigation and global positioning, it's important to convert these coordinates to a global coordinate system.

The conversion process involves applying transformations between the local coordinate system (vehicle/UAV-centered) and a global coordinate system (often GPS-based or map-based). This is achieved by combining the local position with orientation data, using techniques such as pose estimation and rotation matrices.

The homogeneous transformation matrix is commonly used for this purpose:

$$P_{global} = T \cdot P_{local} \quad (6.6)$$

where

- P_{global} - The position in the global coordinate system,

T - The transformation matrix that includes rotation and translation,
 P_{local} - The position in the local coordinate system.

Example: Local to Global Transformation

If the vehicle is located at a position (x_0, y_0) in the local coordinate system and the global coordinate system has an origin at (x_g, y_g) , with a known rotation angle θ , the transformation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_g \\ y_g \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \cos(\theta) - y_0 \sin(\theta) + x_g \\ x_0 \sin(\theta) + y_0 \cos(\theta) + y_g \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.7)$$

This formula helps translate the vehicle's local position to a global position, allowing for accurate navigation and path planning in the real world.

Table 6.1: Types of coordinate systems and transformation techniques used in autonomous systems.

Coordinate System	Description	Transformation Technique
Pixel Coordinates	Coordinates in the image (2D space)	Camera calibration, depth estimation
Local Coordinates	Coordinates relative to the vehicle or UAV's position	Pose estimation, rotation matrices
Global Coordinates	Absolute coordinates (e.g., GPS-based)	Homogeneous transformation, GPS/IMU fusion

By successfully transforming the pixel coordinates to real-world Cartesian coordinates, autonomous systems can make intelligent decisions based on the positions of objects in their environment. This step is essential for tasks like navigation, collision avoidance, and target tracking.

7. System Testing and Evaluation Analysis

7.1 Testing Setup and Protocols

This chapter is delve into the method of evaluating the entire cooperative system regarding its functionality, performance, and reliability. The ways through which the experiment was conducted include simulations in the field, real-life testing, and in-depth analyses of the data collected to ensure the system features meet the standards as stipulated.

Fig. 7.1: System testing environment in real-world validation.

7.2 Detection Accuracy (Precision & Recall)

The accuracy and precision of the object detection and tracking system are critical in ensuring that the IV correctly identifies and classifies players (allies and opponents) based on the data received from the UAV. Accuracy and precision are defined as:

Accuracy (A): The proportion of true results (both true positives and true negatives) to the total number of cases examined. It measures the overall correctness of the detection system.

$$A = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (7.1)$$

where

- TP - True Positives
- TN - True Negatives
- FP - False Positives
- FN - False Negatives

Precision (P): The proportion of true positive results to the total predicted positives. Precision assesses how accurate the positive predictions are.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (7.2)$$

Recall (R): The proportion of true positive results to the total number of actual positives. It measures how well the system identifies all relevant instances.

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (7.3)$$

F1 Score: The harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balance between the two metrics. It is especially

useful when dealing with imbalanced datasets.

$$F1 = 2 \times \frac{P \times R}{P + R} \quad (7.4)$$

7.3 Communication Latency and Targeting Success

Communication latency is the time it takes for information to go from one system to another and thus will be crucial in the real-time decision-making process between the IV and UAV. That said, latency is defined as the measurement from one system to travel to the other. This has an impact on the responsiveness of the IV regarding changes in the environment that it is observing. The (LL) is defined as the time it takes for the messages to travel from the UAV and back to the IV:

$$L = \frac{t_{response}}{n_{data}} \quad (7.5)$$

where

$t_{response}$ - Total time taken for a response after sending data

n_{data} - Number of data packets sent

Measured time differences are for the period a UAV captures an image, processes the data, sends it to the IV, and the latter subsequently reacts to the information. The communication reliability of the system is commonly defined in terms of a successful transmission over failed transmission attempts with respect to a time frame. It is computed as:

$$R = \frac{\text{Successful Transmissions}}{\text{Total Transmissions}} \times 100 \quad (7.6)$$

These metrics are key to determining the performance of both the IV and UAV, especially in cooperative tasks where synchronization and rapid response are essential.

Table 7.1: Test results for latency and reliability environmental conditions.

Test Condition	Average Latency (ms)	Transmission Reliability (%)
Indoor (Line of Sight)	30	98%
Indoor (Obstacles)	70	95%
Outdoor (Clear Sky)	50	96%
Outdoor (Windy)	100	90%

7.4 Comparative Analysis: Haar Cascade vs YOLO for Real-Time Detection

In evaluating real-time object detection capabilities within the cooperative platform, a comparison was made between two prominent image detection algorithms:

Table 7.2: Comparison of Detection Performance Between Haar Cascade and YOLOv5

Criteria	Haar Cascade Classifier	YOLOv5
Detection Accuracy (%)	78%	94%
Precision	0.72	0.91
Recall	0.68	0.93
F1 Score	0.7	0.92
Average Detection Time (ms)	120	35
Frame Rate (fps)	8	28
False Positive Rate	High (12%)	Low (3%)
Hardware Resource Usage	Low (CPU-only)	Moderate to High (GPU needed)
Robustness to Lighting	Poor	Strong
Object Differentiation	Limited (binary or few-class)	Multi-class (bounding boxes + labels)

Haar Cascade Classifier and YOLO (You Only Look Once). These algorithms were tested using identical image datasets obtained from the UAV's onboard camera under varying lighting and obstacle conditions. In this revised section, the table comparing Haar Cascade and YOLOv5 should highlight the advantages of Haar Cascade in terms of speed and low resource usage but also acknowledge its lower detection accuracy and limited robustness in challenging conditions.

YOLOv5 significantly outperformed Haar Cascade in all key metrics, particularly in detection speed, accuracy, and robustness to environmental conditions.

While Haar Cascade is lightweight and easy to implement (suitable for resource-constrained IV systems), its detection capabilities are limited and often generate false positives or fail in poor lighting[58].

YOLO's ability to detect and classify multiple objects in real-time makes it more suitable for dynamic gaming environments requiring instantaneous and precise targeting.

Real-Time Testing Results : This section should also reflect the performance of Haar Cascade under various real-world conditions, noting its strengths in simpler environments but acknowledging its limitations with more dynamic and complex test scenarios.

Table 7.3: Real-Time Detection Performance Under Different Test Conditions

Test Scenario	Haar Cascade Accuracy (%)	YOLOv5 Accuracy (%)
Indoor, controlled lighting	0.82	0.96
Outdoor, daylight	0.75	0.94
Outdoor, low light	0.58	0.89
Opponent player with occlusion	0.6	0.92
Multiple opponent players (3-5)	0.52	0.91

Motivation for selection :

The Haar Cascade Classifier was chosen for initial comparison and testing in this study due to its simplicity, ease of implementation, and low computational overhead. While more advanced algorithms like YOLOv5 offer superior performance in terms of detection accuracy, Haar Cascade has several distinct advantages in certain situations:

(1) **Low Computational Demand:** Haar Cascade operates effectively with limited hardware resources, making it a suitable choice for real-time systems where processing power is constrained (such as the Intelligent Vehicle's onboard system).

(2) **Faster Setup for Simple Applications:** Haar Cascade can be trained quickly and efficiently using relatively small datasets, making it ideal for rapid prototyping or less complex image detection tasks where the environment is controlled and less dynamic.

(3) **Robust to Simple Scenarios:** In simpler environments where there are fewer variables (e.g., static objects or few players), Haar Cascade provides adequate detection performance with reasonable processing speed.

This choice is also motivated by the practical constraints of real-time systems that may not always have access to powerful GPUs, making Haar Cascade a suitable fallback solution for scenarios where speed and resource efficiency are prioritized over advanced detection capabilities.

7.5 UAV Flight Stability and Image Processing Accuracy

Stability in flight of UAVs is assessed in terms of its ability to realize stable flight while ensuring that the images received by the IV are received clearly. Therefore, image processing accuracy was tested against how well the UAV captures images and transmits them for object detection and image classification.

Flight Stability: Measured using the pitch and roll deviations from a straight path, with the following formula

$$S_{flight} = \frac{\text{Max Deviation Angle}}{\text{Time Interval}} \times 100 \tag{7.7}$$

where

S_{flight} - Flight Stability

Image Processing Accuracy: The percentage of correctly classified objects in the images processed by the onboard system. It is calculated as:

$$I_{accuracy} = \frac{\text{Correctly Classified Objects}}{\text{Total Objects}} \times 100 \tag{7.8}$$

where

$I_{accuracy}$ - Image Processing Accuracy

Table 7.4: Result summary of the UAV's stability and image processing accuracy.

Test Condition	Max Deviation (°)	Processing Accuracy (%)
Stable Conditions	5	95%
Windy Conditions	15	90%

Based on the comparison between Haar Cascade and YOLOv5, it is evident that YOLOv5 outperforms Haar Cascade in terms of detection accuracy, speed, and robustness to dynamic and challenging environments. However, Haar Cascade remains a viable option in scenarios with limited computational resources or simpler detection tasks where its faster processing time and lower resource demand can provide adequate results. For the cooperative platform, YOLOv5 is the preferred algorithm due to its superior real-time performance, multi-class detection, and ability to handle dynamic and complex scenarios, which are crucial for the system's success in the field

Conclusion

This research developed a cooperative platform integrating an Intelligent Vehicle (IV) and an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) for real-time object detection and collaboration. The system demonstrated effective multi-agent cooperation for task-sharing and problem-solving in a controlled environment. Key contributions include the design of both the IV and UAV, the application of image processing techniques for object detection, and the evaluation of system performance under various conditions.

The platform has practical applications in gaming, automation, and defense, but challenges such as lighting variability, scalability, and communication latency were identified. Future improvements include integrating AI-driven object detection, expanding to swarm robotics, and enhancing communication protocols with 5G or LoRa technology. The research provides a foundation for the future development of autonomous multi-agent system.

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